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PREVALENCE OF APICAL PERIODONTITIS ON ROOT-FILLED TEETH IN AN ADULT SERBIAN POPULATION

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Abstract:

Introduction: The aim of this study is to report the frequency and distribution of root-filled teeth and the prevalence of apical periodontitis (AP) in an adult population in Serbia.

Material and method: Digital panoramic radiographs of 350 patients who were examined at the Dental Clinic of Vojvodina, Novi Sad were evaluated. Patients under the age of 18 and patients that had less than 7 teeth in both jaws were excluded. The frequency of root canal treatment and periapical status of all teeth present was assessed by two examiners, using the periapical index (PAI) score. Interexaminer correlation test was performed.

Results: Among a total of 8849 examined teeth, 502 teeth were root-filled (5.67%). The number of root-filled teeth with AP present was 293 (58.37% prevalence). The distribution of root-filled teeth was the highest among premolars (190 or 37.85%) and maxillary anterior teeth (152 or 30.28%). However, the prevalence of AP in connection with root-filled teeth was in total higher on molar teeth (112 or 22.31%) and on premolar teeth (104 or 20.72%).

Conclusion: Treatment outcomes of root-filled teeth depend on many factors that should be considered, but also they can vary in different populations as well. The frequency of endodontically treated teeth in this study were higher than in comparable populations in other countries and the prevalence of apical periodontitis were similar compared to other population studies.

Key words: *Apical periodontitis, root-filled teeth, endodontic therapy, population*